

The Effect of Individual Adaptability and Perceived Organizational Support on Performance through Organizational Commitment and Turnover Intention in the Family Support Team in Lamongan Regency

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ABSTRACT: The objective of this research is to determine and examine the influence of individual adaptability and perceived organizational support on member's performance with organizational commitment and also turnover intention as the mediation in Lamongan Regency Family Support Team. Research methodology employs a quantitative approach. Total sample was 354 respondents from a total population of 3.108 members of family support team, using proportional random sampling technique. Hypotheses testing was done using the SEM-AMOS statistical technique on the 8 proposed hypotheses. The results of this research show that: (1) Individual adaptability influences organizational commitment, (2) Individual adaptability has a negative effect on turnover intention, (3) Individual adaptability influences member performance, (4) Perceived organizational support influences organizational commitment, (5) Perceived organizational support has a negative effect on turnover intention, (6) Perceived organizational support influences member performance, (7) Organizational commitment influences member performance, (8) Turnover intention doesn't significantly influence the performance of Family Support Team members in Lamongan Regency.

KEYWORDS: Individual Adaptability, Perceived Organizational Support, Organizational Commitment, Turnover intention, Performance

I. INTRODUCTION

The Family Support Team was formed in light of Regulation of Indonesian Presidential Number 72 on 2021 that pertaining the Acceleration of Stunting Reduction. The Family Support Team consists of midwives, empowering family welfare cadres and family planning cadres who are tasked with carrying out family support in reducing the prevalence of stunting. The rate of stunting in Lamongan Regency in 2022 was still high and ranked 5th highest in East Java, so the performance of the Lamongan Regency Family Support Team members needs to be studied further. According to Laili *et al* (2022), the role of the Family Facilitator Team as the main human resource is indispensable in efforts to prevent and assist stunting targets.

As a newly formed team in 2021, Family Support Team members need adaptation in completing their duties and responsibilities. The adaptability of Family Support Team members in adjusting tasks needs to be a concern, because it can affect the performance of these members and the team. Individual adaptability is a predictor factor that has a strong effect on individual performance and work achievement (Murphy, 2015).

Organizational support in the Family Support Team is needed in the smooth running of tasks and achievement of goals. Perceived organizational support perceived by Family Support Team members can ultimately be the basis for the organization to improve the commitment and performance of its members. Perceived Organizational Support will have a direct relationship with the output performance of employees or other organization members. The positive perception of organizational support, it will create organizational justice, which can motivate members to to give the organization their best performance (Biswas & Kapil, 2017).

In achieving organizational goals, Family Support Team members must have a strong commitment to always be tied to the team. The attachment and willingness of members in the team is manifested in organizational commitment. Organizational commitment shows a strong role in creating better member performance. Because with this commitment, members have stronger beliefs and high devotion which have an impact on their performance (Chiu et al., 2020).

In research by Zhu et al (2022), strong organizational commitment will reduce the desire to move or leave. Turnover intention refers to a person's intention to quit and look for other employment alternatives. Turnover intention in an organization can affect individual working and the organization performance. In organizations with low turnover rates, members will have better performance than organizations with high turnover rates (Asamoah et al., 2014).

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This is inversely proportional to the research of Sumantri *et al* (2017), the intention of an employee to leave has no impact on the worker's output performance. The difference in the study's conclusion shows that there is a gap in facts in each field regarding the relationship between turnover intention and employee performance. Satyawati dan Eko (2018), in their research concluded that individual adaptability affects organizational commitment. Organizational commitment and adaptability also affect employee performance. Recommendations in this study suggest further research related to organizational support variables.

On the basis of the research results and phenomena above, it is necessary to conduct in-depth research on the Effect of Individual Adaptability and Perceived Organizational Support on Performance Through Organizational Commitment and Turnover Intention in the Lamongan Regency Family Support Team.

II. THEORETICAL STUDY

A. Organizational Behaviour Theory

Organizational Behavior Theory is the theory of how people behave inside an organization and what they behave in influencing organizational performance. In this case, organizational behavior is related to how to act and react, both to individual performance, groups and organizational levels (Robbins dan Judge, 2017).

Organizational behavior is an in-depth study of how individuals, groups and organizations interact in a work environment. A crucial component of organizational development is the human resources element. Organizational behavior summarizes various components involving humans in organizations, such as: ability, motivation, commitment, leadership, communication and organizational support. By understanding organizational behavior, it can be known the relationship between people who work in the workplace and how organizations can use their human resources most efficiently to achieve common goals (Rodiyana, 2016)

B. Individual Adaptability

According to Pulakos et al in Murphy (2015), individual adaptability is an adaptive performance that explains situations in which people adapt their conduct to fit the requirements of novel circumstances or events or environmental changes. An individual's capacity, aptitude, attitude, readiness, and drive to modify or adapt to various tasks, social situations, and environmental factors is reflected in their individual adaptability.

Indicators of individual adaptability according to Ployhart & Bliese (2015), are :

1. Learning
2. Intrapersonal
3. Culture
4. Work Stress
5. Uncertainty

C. Perceived Organizational Support

Perceived Organizational Support defined as an organizations member view or assumption of the degree to which an organization give and cares about their contributions and cares about employee welfare (Rhoades & Eisenberger (2002).

There are three important indicators of perceived organizational support, namely:

1. Procedural Justice
2. Supervisor Support
3. Organizational Rewards and Working Conditions

D. Organizational Commitment

According to Allen dan Meyer in Yusuf & Syarif (2018), organizational commitment is a belief that binds individuals or workers to the institution which is indicated by an attitude of loyalty, a sense of involvement with duty tasks, belief in the organization's principles and objectives. Indicators of organizational commitment according to Mowday, Steers, Porter in Wardhana (2021), are listed below :

1. Affective Commitment
2. Continuance commitment
3. Normative Commitment

E. Turnover Intention

Mobley in Karomah (2020), turnover intention, which relates to an individual's assessment of whether or not to continue his association with the company and has not demonstrated clear action to quit the organization, is the desire (intention) to leave the organization. Mobley states that three signs are utilized to gauge the intention to turnover, namely :

1. Thinking of quitting
2. Intention to search for alternatives
3. Intention to quit

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F. Performance

According to Prawirosentono in Budiyanto & Mochklas (2020), performance is the outcome of work completed by workers or members of an organization in line with their responsibilities or authority within that particular organization. Bernadin & Russell in Adamy (2016) clarifies that individual performance is the outcome of a person's labor as determined by the responsibility and authority given to him. Individual performance is the achievement of a person based on his power and duty in accordance with the objectives of the company successfully and efficiently (Kairupan., 2021).

Based on the concept of Bernadin & Russell in Adamy (2016), There are three indicators that are appropriate in measuring member performance, namely :

1. Work Quality, concerns the degree to which the activities' implementation process or outcomes are nearly in line with the desired outcomes;
2. Work Quantity, concerns the quantity generated, such as the sum of money, the quantity of units, the quantity of cycles, or the quantity of completed activities;
3. Time Effectiveness, the degree to which a task is finished within the allotted time.

III. CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

According to the conceptual framework mentioned above, the following is the research hypothesis:

- H1 : Individual adaptability influences positive effect on organizational commitment in Family Support Team members.
H2 : Individual adaptability influences negative effect on the turnover intention of Family Support Team members.
H3 : Individual adaptability influences positive effect on the performance of Family Support Team members.
H4 : Perceived organizational support influences positive effect on organizational commitment in Family Support Team members.
H5 : Perceived organizational support influences negative effect on the turnover intention of Family Support Team members.
H6 : Perceived organizational support influences positive effect on the performance of Family Support Team members.
H7 : Organizational commitment influences positive effect on the performance of Family Support Team members.
H8 : Turnover intention influences positive effect on the performance of Family Support Team members.

IV. RESEARCH METHOD

A. Data Type and Sources

This study uses a quantitative approach with explanatory research, which aims to test the hypothesis in examining the effect of independent variables, that are individual adaptability and perceived organizational support, then mediating variables are organizational commitment and turnover intention, and the dependent variable is performance. Primary data sources in this study used a five-point Likert scale in a structured questionnaire. data examination utilizing SEM-AMOS statistical techniques.

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B. Population and Sample

Population on this research were members of the Family Support Team in Lamongan Regency, with a total of 3,108 Family Support Team members. The number of samples examined was, as can be seen from the Slovin formula calculation, the sample numbers obtained was 354 respondents. Sampling was conducted using proportional random sampling technique.

C. Data Collection

In this research, interviews are the method used in this study to obtain data with respondents, through questionnaires with online filling (*Google form*)

D. Data Analysis Method

Data analysis using AMOS SEM statistical techniques. Analysis with AMOS was used in this research, because it is able to analyze the relationship hypothesis on several variables, in a large sample size. The Critical Ratio (CR) and Probability (P) values are analyzed in order to determine the Regression Weight value. For the CR value and P value, the necessary limits are < 1.96 and ≤ 0.05 , respectively. The study hypothesis may be approved if data processing findings indicate a CR value of ≥ 1.96 and P value of < 0.05 .

V. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

A. Evaluation of Measurement Model Fit

Figure 2. Measurement Model Fit

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The following table displays the findings of the measurement model fit test as per Figure 2:

Table 1. Fit Measure in the Measurement Model

		Critical Value	Measurement Model	
			Index value	Keterangan
Absolute Fit Indices	Prob. χ^2	> 0,05	0,000	<i>Even a good fit</i>
	Cmin/df	$\leq 3,00$	1,287	<i>Good fit</i>
	GFI	$\geq 0,90$	0,883	<i>Marginal fit</i>
	RMSEA	$\leq 0,08$	0,087	<i>Marginal fit</i>
	SRMR	$\leq 0,08$	0,021	<i>Good fit</i>
Incremental Fit Indices	CFI	$\geq 0,95$	0,967	<i>Good fit</i>
	TLI	$\geq 0,95$	0,959	<i>Good fit</i>
	NFI	$\geq 0,90$	0,962	<i>Good fit</i>
	RFI	$\geq 0,90$	0,953	<i>Good fit</i>
Parsimony Fit Indices	AGFI	$\geq 0,90$	0,835	<i>Marginal fit</i>

^(a) Even when the probability value is below 0.05 or even a good fit, the model is still fit in models with a sample size of $n > 250$ or numerous indicators $m > 30$. (Hair et al., 2018: 642).

Source : SEM AMOS Output

The fit test of the measurement model is displayed in the above table yielded good fit criteria, and that each criterion satisfied both the good fit and marginal fit requirements. A marginal fit indicates that the model's fit is within allowable bounds, whereas a good fit indicates that the model fits well. As a result, it may be said that the measurement model fits data well and acceptably. After the measurement model fit test, convergent validity is utilized to assess the construct validity. In generally, if a construct's indicators possess a factor loading (standardized regression weight) value of at least 0.50, it is said to achieve convergent validity (Hair et al., 2018).

Table 2. Construct Validity Test

Construct	Indicator	Factor Loadings	Description
Individual Adaptability (X1)	Learning (X1.1)	0,930	Valid
	Interpersonal (X1.2)	0,928	Valid
	Culture (X1.3)	0,933	Valid
	Managing Work Stress (X1.4)	0,872	Valid
	Uncertainty (X1.5)	0,912	Valid
Perceived Organizational Support (X2)	Procedural Justice (X2.1)	0,954	Valid
	Superior Support (X2.2)	0,948	Valid
	Rewards & Working Conditions (X2.3)	0,916	Valid
Organizational Commitment (Z1)	Affective Commitment (Z1.1)	0,929	Valid
	Continuance Commitment (Z1.2)	0,867	Valid
	Normative Commitment (Z1.3)	0,952	Valid
Turnover Intention (Z2)	Thinking of Quitting (Z2.1)	0,922	Valid
	Intention to Search for Alternatives (Z2.2)	0,961	Valid
	Intention to Quit (Z2.3)	0,964	Valid
Performance (Y)	Work Quality (Y.1)	0,853	Valid
	Work Quantity (Y.2)	0,970	Valid
	Time Effectiveness (Y.3)	0,958	Valid

Source : SEM AMOS Output

The table above shows the all indicators in construct validity evaluation results show that the measuring model produces factor loading values more than 0.50, demonstrating the validity of these indicators in developing the constructs of individual adaptability, perceived organizational support, organizational commitment, turnover intention, and member performance, thus meeting convergent validity.

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Table 3. Construct Reliability Test

Variable	Construct Reliability	AVE	Description
Individual Adaptability (X1)	0,963	0,838	Reliabel
Perceived Organizational Support (X2)	0,958	0,883	Reliabel
Organizational Commitment (Z1)	0,940	0,840	Reliabel
Turnover Intention (Z2)	0,965	0,901	Reliabel
Performance (Y)	0,949	0,862	Reliabel
Rule of thumbs	$\geq 0,70$	$\geq 0,50$	

Source : SEM AMOS Output

Based on each variable yields the construct reliability values more than 0.70 and an AVE value more than 0.50, according to the findings of the construct reliability study, so it is concluded that the indicators that measure the constructs of individual adaptability, perceived organizational support, organizational commitment, turnover intention, and member performance, are declared reliable.

B. Evaluation of Structural Model Fit

Figure 3. Structural Model Fit

The outcomes of the structural model fit test demonstrate that the conditions (good fit and marginal fit) have been met, and the requirements for the parsimony, incremental, and absolute fit indices have all been satisfied. As a result, the structural model is reasonable. A strong fit with empirical data is when the model created for this study fits the data well; a marginal fit occurs when the model fits the data within reasonable bounds.

Individual adaptability and perceived organizational support have 91.7 percent impact on organizational commitment among Family Support Team members in Lamongan Regency, while the remaining 8.3 percent is affected by additional variables. The value of RZ22 is 0.227, indicating that the proportion of the impact of individual adaptability and perceived organizational support

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on turnover intention among Family Support Team members in Lamongan Regency is 22.7 percent, whereas other factors have an impact on the remaining 77.3 percent. Additionally, RY2 has a value of 0.860, meaning that the percentage of the influence of individual adaptability, perceived organizational support, organizational commitment, and turnover intention on member performance on Family Support Team members in Lamongan Regency is 86.0 percent, while other factors have an impact on the remaining 14.0%.

With a total coefficient of determination (R2 total) of 0.905, it can be concluded that approximately 0,905 of the data variety can be explained by the conceptual model created for this investigation. Otherwise, this study's model has outstanding predictive significance. or is relevant to be used to predict the performance of Family Support Team members through individual adaptability, perceived organizational support, organizational commitment, and turnover intention.

C. Direct and Indirect Effect Analysis

These are the outcomes of testing each hypothesis of the direct effect of individual adaptability and perceived organizational support on organizational commitment, turnover intention, and member performance in the Family Support Team in Lamongan Regency.

Table 4. Testing the Direct Effect Hypothesis

Direct Effect	Std. Estimate	C.R.	P-value	Hypothesis Decision
Individual Adaptability → Organizational Commitment	0,48	11,898	0,004	H1 Accepted
Individual Adaptability → Turnover Intention	-0,15	-2,039	0,042	H2 Accepted
Individual Adaptability → Performance	0,33	5,962	0,003	H3 Accepted
Perceived Organizational Support → Organizational Commitment	0,50	12,600	0,021	H4 Accepted
Perceived Organizational Support → Turnover Intention	-0,34	-3,818	0,011	H5 Accepted
Perceived Organizational Support → Performance	0,23	4,010	0,011	H6 Accepted
Organizational Commitment → Performance	0,37	4,926	0,009	H7 Accepted
Turnover Intention → Performance	-0,04	-1,125	0,261	H8 Not Accepted

SE, CR, & p-values based on bootstrapping bias-corrected percentile method

Source: SEM AMOS Output

The findings of the direct effect hypothesis testing in this research show about :

1. With a significance value (p-value) of 0.004 (below the real level of 5%) and an estimated coefficient of influence of individual adaptability on organizational commitment of 11.898 (higher than 1.96), the relationship between the two variables is significant. With a positive coefficient of effect of 0.48, the organizational commitment is positively correlated with an individual's level of flexibility. Consequently, the first hypothesis, which claims that organizational commitment is significantly impacted by individual flexibility, in Family Support Team members in Lamongan Regency, can be accepted (H1 accepted). This is consistent with studies Collie et al (2018) and Rudolph et al (2017), which proves that individual adaptability show the positive influences on organizational commitment. This result is also supported by research of Satyawati & Eko (2018), with an increase in the adaptability of members, it will further increase organizational commitment.
2. The approximated impact coefficient of individual adaptability on turnover intention shows the significant influence with a CR value of -2.039 (the absolute value is higher than 1.96 and a p-value (significance value) of 0.042, which is lower than 5%. Because of the ensuing negative coefficient of effect of -0.15, the turnover intention is inversely correlated with an individual's level of adaptability. Consequently, the second theory, which asserts that Individual flexibility significantly influences the inclination to leave a job. in Family Support Team members in Lamongan Regency, acceptable as well (H2 accepted). The findings are in accordance with the research of Rasheed et al. (2020), C. Sun et al (2023) and Fauziah (2022), proving that individual adaptability has a notable and reduce impact on the intention to turnover. Also in line with research of Lee et al (2021), stated that individual adaptability allows members to effectively adjust to modifications in the workplace. This then leads to a positive attitude of members towards tasks in the organization, thereby reducing members' intention to move.
3. With a the p-value, or significance level of 0.003 (lower than 5%) and an estimated coefficient of variation of 5.962 (more than 1.96), the effect of individual adaptability on member performance is shown to be significant. The outcome is a positive coefficient of effect of 0.33, indicating that members perform better the more adaptive each individual is. Thus, the third hypothesis, according to which performance is significantly impacted by individual adaptability, of Family Support Team members in Lamongan Regency, can also be accepted (H3 accepted). This is in accordance with the research results Kalwar et al (2023) and Zebua et al (2021), which proves that individual adaptability significantly impacts each member's performance. Research of Sony & Mekoth (2016), explains that a individual adaptability is an important component in creating individual performance, because adaptability forms better knowledge and work skills..

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4. The approximated impact coefficient of the effect of perceived organizational support a significant influence is observed on organizational commitment, as evidenced by a CR value of 12.600 (higher than 1.96) and a significance value (p-value) of 0.021 (lower than the genuine level of 5%). With a positive coefficient of effect of 0.50, the stronger the organizational commitment, the higher the perceived organizational support. Therefore, it is possible to accept the fourth hypothesis (H4 accepted), which claims that family support team members in Lamongan Regency's perception of organizational support significantly influences their organizational commitment. The findings of this study are supported by earlier studies, specifically that conducted by Arshadi (2011), Pradita et al (2022) and L. Sun (2019), which proves that organizational commitment is significantly impacted by perceived organizational support.. Research results Garg and Dhar (2014), shows that the perception of high employee organizational support can lead to increased employee commitment to their organization.

5. The p-value, or significance value of 0.011 ($< 5\%$) and an estimated coefficient of -3.828 (the absolute value is more than 1.96) on the impact of turnover intention and perceived organizational support, the effect is clearly significant. The effect coefficient that is obtained is -0.34 (negative), indicating that the intention to leave an organization decreases as perceived organizational support increases. Consequently, the fifth hypothesis, according to which turnover intention is significantly influenced by perceived organizational support in Family Support Team members in Lamongan Regency, can also be accepted (H5 accepted). Research from Gao et al (2020) and Oktaviani (2018) supports the results of this study, which prove that perceived organizational support has a significant and negative effect on turnover intention. Additionally consistent with research Putu et al (2017), the high perception of assistance given by the institution to members can reduce the desire of members to leave their organization.

6. The significance value (p-value) of 0.011, which is below the actual 5% threshold, and an estimated coefficient of influence of felt organizational support on member performance of 4.010, which is larger than 1.96, indicates a substantial effect. With a positive coefficient of effect of 0.23, members perform better when they perceive greater organizational support. Consequently, the sixth hypothesis, according to which performance is significantly impacted by perceived organizational support of Family Support Team members in Lamongan Regency, can also be accepted (H6 accepted). This is consistent with studies by Atom et al (2023), Jeong & Kim (2022), and Cullen et al (2014), which proves that perceived support from the organization significantly influences on individual performance. Research by Syaifudin & Sopiyan (2023) also supports this study results, which claims that institutional support felt by members can directly improve member performance.

7. The significance value (p-value) of 0.009, this is lower than the actual 5% threshold and an estimated coefficient of the influence of organizational commitment on member performance of 4.926, which is larger than 1.96, the effect is clearly significant. The resultant coefficient of effect is 0.37, which is positive, indicating that member performance increases with organizational commitment. Thus, according to the seventh hypothesis, organizational commitment significantly influences the performance of Family Support Team members in Lamongan Regency, can also be accepted (H7 accepted). This is in accordance with the research results of Rita et al (2018), Irvan et al (2022), Burhannudin et al (2019), and Duwika et al (2023), proving that organizational commitment has a noteworthy impact on individual performance. The study's findings include show similarities with research by Loan (2020), which shows that strong organizational commitment is able to show emotional attachment and a sense of responsibility through high performance.

8. With a significance value (p-value) of 0.261, which is greater than the actual 5% threshold, and an estimated coefficient of -1.125, which indicates an absolute value less than 1.96, the influence of turnover intention on member performance is not statistically significant. The larger turnover intention has no discernible influence on performance deterioration, as evidenced by the ensuing effect coefficient of just -0.04 (statistically equivalent to zero). Thus, the eighth hypothesis, which claims that performance is significantly impacted by turnover intention in Family Support Team members in Lamongan Regency, cannot be accepted (H8 rejected). The insignificant study result are in accordance with research from Sumantri et al (2017), which proves that individual performance is not much impacted by a person's intention to leave a firm or organization.. Research by Adiyono and Wajdi (2023), also proves the same result, where turnover intention has no appreciable impact on an individual's performance inside the organization.

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programs must focus to various aspects in achieving the stunting reduction target. Various aspects that need to be developed by stakeholders are through increasing budgets, personnel, awards, facilities, training and policies related to accelerating stunting reduction programs. In future research, it can be considered to add other variables that can affect individual performance, such as work involvement, workload and job satisfaction.

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